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PERSONAL DATA PROTECTION IN THE AGE OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION: STATUS, CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

Abstract: *In the contemporary world, information technologies are part of our social existence. Digitalization is becoming an essential part of society based on new ways of interaction between people, companies and the public sector. As the process of digital transformation intensifies, more industries as well as the public sector are increasingly transformed to a lesser or greater extent. Digital transformation is an intricate process which implies much more than just the implementation of technical devices. It requires a new way of thinking and acting at all levels. Today, the collection, storage, processing and transfer of personal data is present in every sphere of life, especially in the digital sphere. The huge development of technology, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and the Internet of Things (IoT) stand out as the major challenges in terms of ensuring privacy and protection of personal data in the contemporary circumstances. The paper analyses the European legal framework for the protection of personal data, starting from the first international agreement in this area, the "Convention 108", adopted by the Council of Europe, and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which establishes common standards in the EU. In this regard, the establishment of key principles for the processing of personal data guarantees the rights of individuals. Given the undeniable importance of privacy and personal data protection, as well as the adopted regulations, for the implementation of these rights, the question is whether modern legislation provides sufficient protection of these important rights, as well as whether institutions and organizations can fully*

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implement and respect them. Accordingly, institutions and organizations have to adapt in technological and organizational terms, to reconsider the collection, storage, processing and transmission of data, to change the way of thinking and foster a culture of digital ethics.

Keywords: *personal data protection, privacy, digital transformation, Convention 108, GDPR.*

1. Introduction

In the contemporary conditions, information technologies are part of our social existence, and digitization is becoming an essential part of society based on new ways of interaction between people, companies and the public sector. Most of us have been hearing the term “digital transformation” pretty much everywhere for a few years now. Entire industries were transformed and moved a great deal of their activity online, embracing technologies like cloud storage, Internet of Things, etc. As the digital transformation process increasingly intensifies, more industries as well as the public sector are being transformed to a lesser or greater extent. Digital transformation is a comprehensive process which implies much more than just implementing technical tools; it calls for a new way of thinking and acting at all levels.¹ However, given the different paces of digital transformation in different countries, the development of digital transformation differs in terms of the operation of administration and government bodies, the provision of electronic services, including transactional digital services, etc.

Today, the collection, storage, processing and transfer of personal data is present in every sphere of life, but it is particularly prominent in the digital sphere. With the development of digitalization and moving towards digital platforms and services, the amount of collected, processed, transmitted and stored data (including personal data) is growing, which inevitably generates intricate threats and activities aimed at exploiting the valuable data reserves. In such circumstances, the huge development of technology, Artificial Intelligence (AI), and Internet of Things (IoT) stand out as major challenges in terms of ensuring privacy and protecting personal data. Protecting such data from unauthorized access, breaches, and other forms of cyber threats has become a paramount concern for businesses, public bodies and individuals.

¹ Forbes (2022). What Data Privacy really needs now is a Digital Transformation, (by G. Ringel), 31.3.2022, <https://www.forbes.com/councils/forbestechcouncil/2022/03/31/what-data-privacy-really-needs-now-is-a-digital-transformation/>.

As the digital landscape continues to evolve, the potential risks to data privacy are likely to increase. It is crucial for organizations in the private or public sector to proactively anticipate and address these challenges to safeguard the privacy and security of their customers' data. Organizations should adopt a proactive and holistic approach to data privacy, in order to mitigate risks and comply with regulations, which will lead to increased trust.

Considering the various digital transformation levels in different countries and the ongoing use of manual approaches to service provision, the question arises whether the legislation on privacy protection, which should mark the future of technology-based relationships, fully follows the digital transformation progress, and whether privacy protection is advancing or stagnating.

2. Definition and principles of personal data protection

Before focusing on the personal data protection, it is necessary to define the personal data and data processing, and to outline the core principles of personal data protection.

The United Nations (UN) defines personal data as “information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (“data subject”), by, or on behalf of, the UN System Organizations in carrying out their mandated activities” (United Nations, 2018: 1). Pursuant to the Council of Europe Convention ETS No. 108 for the protection of individuals with regard to automatic processing of personal data,² “personal data” means any information relating to an identified or identifiable individual (“data subject”). Under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)³, the EU's main data protection law, Article 4(1) of the GDPR provides that “personal data means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ('data subject'): an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person.” Different pieces of information which may lead to one's identification may also be considered personal data.

² Article 2 of the CoE Convention for the Protection of Individuals with regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data, European Treaty Series - No. 108, Council of Europe, Strasbourg, 28.I.1981, Art. 2, available at: <https://rm.coe.int/1680078b37>.

³ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (*General Data Protection Regulation*), available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj/eng>.

Under the GDPR, “data processing means any operation or a set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction of personal data” (Art. 4(2) GDPR). Notably, Recital 15 of the GDPR states the aim to be technology-neutral in processing personal data, without being dependent on any techniques used (Ramakrishnan, 2022:1). It should apply to both automated and manual processing of personal data if personal data are contained or are intended to be contained in a structured filing system.

The UN outlines several core principles that are the cornerstone of personal data processing, applying to personal data in any form and regardless of the processing method. They are: fair and lawful processing, purpose specification, proportionality and necessity, data retention, accuracy, confidentiality, security, transparency, cross-border data transfers, and accountability (UN, 2018: 2). Article 5 of the GDPR sets out seven fundamental principles: lawfulness, fairness and transparency; purpose limitation; data minimization; storage limitation; accuracy; integrity and confidentiality; and accountability. These personal data processing principles must be observed by both public and private entities when handling personal data.

The personal data processing may be carried out by individuals or by private or public entities, including companies and public authorities. Under the GDPR, individuals have several rights over their personal data, such as: right to be informed, right of access, right to rectification, right to erasure (“right to be forgotten”), right to restriction of processing, right to data portability, right to object, and rights in relation to automated decision-making and profiling (Articles 15-22 GDPR). However, personal data protection does not imply granting individuals absolute control over the use of their personal data in the digital environment. Rather, it involves protecting the accuracy of personal data in the course of processing as well as empowering the data subject by making the person aware of the purposes, methods and objects of data processing and transmission. Concurrently, it implies the handler or processor’s obligation to ensure the legal processing and transmission of personal data in accordance with the rule of law and social ethics (Thiên Tú, Kim Thế Nguyễn, Khanh, Nguyễn Dũng, 2021: 160).

3. Legal framework for personal data protection – international standards

For a long time, privacy and personal data protection has been envisaged as one of the fundamental human rights in international law but lacked proper legal safeguards.

The UN framework does not recognize personal data protection as a fundamental right. Article 12 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR)⁴ was the first international instrument which envisaged the right to respect for private and family life, thus laying down the right to protection of one's private sphere against intrusion of others, especially the state. Article 17 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR)⁵ proclaimed that "no one shall be subjected to arbitrary or unlawful interference with his privacy, family, home or correspondence, nor to unlawful attacks on his honor and reputation", noting that every person is entitled to seek legal protection against such interferences. The impact of new technologies on human rights at the international level was first expressed during the 1968 International Conference on Human Rights in Tehran, which resulted in the adoption of UN Resolution 2450 (XXIII) on 19 December 1968.⁶ More recently, the UN Resolution on the Promotion, Protection and Enjoyment of Human Rights on the Internet (2013)⁷ affirms that the rights that people have offline must also be protected online, particularly freedom of expression (Nastić, 2021: 77). Since 2013, the UN has adopted several resolutions on privacy issues. Notably, the UN Resolution on the right to privacy in the digital age (2013) and Revised draft resolution on the right to privacy in the digital age" (2014)⁸ were adopted in response to the development of new

⁴ The UN Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), adopted by the UN General Assembly on 10 December 1948; <https://www.un.org/en/about-us/universal-declaration-of-human-rights>.

⁵ The UN International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR), adopted by the UN General Assembly on 19 December 1966, entered into force in 1976; <https://treaties.un.org/doc/publication/unts/volume%20999/volume-999-i-14668-english.pdf>.

⁶ UN Resolution on Human Rights and Scientific and Technological Developments (1968) UNGA 65: A/RES/2450 (XXIII), UN General Assembly, 19 December 1968, https://digitallibrary.un.org/record/202686/files/A_RES_2450%28XXIII%29-EN.pdf

⁷ UN Resolution 26/13 adopted by the Human Rights Council: The promotion, protection and enjoyment of human rights on the Internet, A/HRC/RES/26/13, 14 July 2014; <https://www.refworld.org/legal/resolution/unhrc/2014/en/105395>.

⁸ See: UN General Assembly Resolution on the right to privacy in the digital age, A/RES/68/167, New York, 18 December 2013; UN General Assembly Revised draft resolution on the right to privacy in the digital age, A/C.3/69/L.26/Rev.1, New York, 19 November 2014; UN General Assembly Revised draft resolution on the right to privacy in the digital age, A/C.3/71/

technologies and whistle-blowing on mass surveillance undertaken in some states (the Snowden leak). Although these resolutions were not legally binding, they sparked an important international, high-level political debate about privacy, new technologies and surveillance. They also contributed to establishing a Special Rapporteur on the right to privacy, with a mandate to promote and protect this right. The rapporteur's specific tasks include gathering information on national practices and experiences in relation to privacy and the challenges arising from new technologies, identifying potential obstacles, and exchange and promotion of best practice. Additionally, revised resolutions adopted in 2016 and 2017 reaffirmed the need to limit the powers of intelligence agencies and condemn mass surveillance (EU FRA, CoE, 2018: 22). The UN Resolution on Promotion and protection of human rights in the context of digital technologies (2023)⁹ reaffirms that the fundamental human rights and freedoms must be protected both online and offline. Thus, Member States shall ensure that "particular attention is paid to access, affordability, digital literacy, privacy and online safety, to enhance the use of digital technologies to mainstream a disability, gender and racial equality perspective in policy decisions and the frameworks that guide them" (Recital 11 of the UN Resolution 2023).

In the European context, the right to privacy was affirmed in the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR),¹⁰ which provides that everyone has the right to respect for his/her private and family life, home and correspondence. Interference with this right by a public authority is prohibited, except where it is in accordance with the law, pursues important and legitimate public interests, and is necessary in a democratic society (Article 8 ECHR). Yet, both the UDHR and the ECHR were adopted well before the development of computers, the Internet and the information society. While these technological advancements have brought significant benefits to individuals and society (enhancing quality of life, efficiency, and productivity), they have also generated new challenges and risks to the right to respect for private life. In response to the need for specific rules governing the collection and use of

L.39/ Rev.1, New York, 16 November 2016; UN Human Rights Council Resolution: The right to privacy in the digital age, A/HRC/34/L.7/Rev.1, 22 March 2017.

⁹ UN General Assembly Resolution on Promotion and protection of human rights in the context of digital technologies A/RES/78/213 (2023), adopted on 19 December 2023; available at: <https://docs.un.org/en/A/RES/78/213#:~:text=19.,20>.

¹⁰ The European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR, 1950), amended by Protocols Nos. 11, 14 and 15 supplemented by Protocols Nos. 1, 4, 6, 7, 12, 13 and 16, Council of Europe/CoE and the European Court of Human Rights/ECtHR, Strasbourg, France; available at: https://www.echr.coe.int/documents/d/echr/convention_ENG.

personal information, a new concept of privacy emerged, known in some jurisdictions as 'informational privacy' and in others as the 'right to informational self-determination'. This concept led to the development of special regulations on personal data protection (EU FRA, CoE, 2018: 18).

The Council of Europe (CoE) adopted various resolutions¹¹ on personal data protection, referring to Article 8 of the ECHR, but the first international legally binding instrument in the data protection field was the CoE 1981 Convention for the protection of individuals with regard to automatic processing of personal data (Convention 108).¹² Convention 108 applies to all data processing carried out by both the private and public sectors, including data processing by the judiciary and law enforcement authorities. It protects individuals against abuses that may accompany the processing of personal data, and concurrently regulates the transborder flows of personal data. The Convention laid down the personal data processing principles which would ensure fair and lawful collection and automatic processing of data for specified legitimate purposes. It also enshrines the individual's right to know that information is stored on him/her and to have it corrected if needed. In addition, the Convention provides for the free flow of personal data between the Contracting Parties and imposes some restrictions on flows to states where legal regulation does not provide equivalent protection (EU FRA, CoE, 2018: 24, 25).

Additional Protocol to the Convention 108, adopted in 2001,¹³ introduced provisions on transborder data flows to non-parties, so-called third countries, and on the mandatory establishment of national data protection supervisory authorities. As a result of the new daily challenges to human rights and fundamental freedoms, particularly to the right to private life, it was clear that the Convention should be modernised in order to better address emerging privacy challenges resulting from the increasing use of new information and communication technologies, the globalisation of processing operations, and the ever-increasing flows of personal data; concurrently, it

¹¹ See: Council of Europe, Committee of Ministers (1973). Resolution (73) 22 on the protection of the privacy of individuals vis-à-vis electronic data banks in the private sector, 26 September 1973; CoE, Committee of Ministers (1974). Resolution (74) 29 on the protection of the privacy of individuals vis-à-vis electronic data banks in the public sector, 20 September 1974.

¹² CoE Convention for the Protection of Individuals with regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data, CETS No. 108 (Convention 108), Council of Europe, 1981; available at: <https://rm.coe.int/1680078b37#...>

¹³ Additional Protocol to the Convention for the Protection of Individuals with regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data regarding supervisory authorities and transborder data flows, European Treaty Series - No. 181, Strasbourg, 8.XI.2001.

was necessary to strengthen the Convention's evaluation and follow up mechanism (CoE Draft Explanatory Report, 2016: 1). The modernisation process was completed by adopting a Protocol (CETS No. 223/2018) amending the Convention 108.¹⁴ This Convention reaffirms important data processing principles and provides new rights to individuals, while simultaneously increasing the responsibilities of entities that process personal data and ensuring their greater accountability. To counter the increased use of profiling, the Convention also establishes the right of individuals not to be subject to decisions solely based on automated data processing without taking into account their own views (EU FRA, CoE, 2018: 27).

Under EU law, data protection has been acknowledged as a distinct fundamental right. It is affirmed in Article 16 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU (TFEU). Article 8 of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights not only affirms the right to personal data protection but also spells out the associated core values. It provides that the personal data processing of must be fair, for specified purposes, and based either on the consent of the person concerned or a legitimate basis laid down by law. Individuals must have the right to access their personal data and to have the data rectified, and compliance with this right must be subject to control by an independent authority (EU FRA, CoE, 2018: 19).

The first formal regulatory act in the area of data protection and privacy rights was the EU Data Protection Directive (1995),¹⁵ which was a cornerstone in the development of further EU legal regulations.¹⁶ As directives do not apply directly and must be transposed into the national laws of the EU Member States. However, in practice, the EU Member States had different

¹⁴ See: Protocol CETS No. 223 amending the Convention for the Protection of Individuals with regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data, CoE Treaty Series - No. 223, Strasbourg, 10.X.2018; available at: <https://rm.coe.int/16808ac918>.

¹⁵ See: Directive 95/46/EC on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (Data Protection Directive), OJ 1995 L 281 (in effect until May 2018).

¹⁶ See: Directive 2002/58/EC concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications sector (Directive on privacy and electronic communications), OJ 2002 L 201, Directive amending the Directive on privacy and electronic communications (Directive 2006/24/EC) and (Directive 2009/136/EC), Council Framework Decision 2008/977/JHA on the protection of personal data processed in the framework of police and judicial cooperation in criminal matters and Directive 2016/680 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by competent authorities for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, and on the free movement of such data.

approaches in transposing the Directive into their laws, which resulted in establishing diverse data protection rules across the EU. Additionally, there were significant differences and changes in information technology and digital transformation. Thus, in 2016, the EU adopted new legislation, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), in order to adapt data protection rules to the digital age. Some of the new rights and obligations that are envisaged in the GDPR are: new or changed basic principles, such as fairness and legality, transparency, accuracy, etc.; new definitions of key terms; authorized persons for data protection; special rules related to minors; new method of application and new sanctions; the right to digital oblivion' the right to data portability; regulations related to security and "leakage" of data; risk assessment, etc. However, the direct application of the GDPR does not exclude the adoption of national regulations in the field of data protection. National laws in this area are necessary because the GDPR has left many open clauses (Diligenski, Prlja, Cerović, 2018: 12).

The GDPR emphasizes the importance of obtaining explicit consent from individuals for data collection and processing. It also highlights the need for effective data governance and accountability within organizations. One of the key challenges posed by the GDPR is the "right to be forgotten", which allows individuals to request the erasure of their personal data. The GDPR has also caused a cultural shift within organizations, emphasizing the importance of data ethics and accountability. It emphasizes the principle of data minimization, requiring organizations to collect and process only the personal data that is necessary for specific purposes. The GDPR has also brought attention to the ethical implications of automated decision-making and profiling. It grants individuals the right not to be subject to solely automated decisions that have legal or other significant effects. This provision aims to protect individuals from potentially biased or discriminatory algorithms. Selbst and Powles (2017) explore the challenges of implementing the right to explanation under the GDPR and argue for greater transparency and accountability in algorithmic decision-making (Ullagaddi, 2024: 29-35).

In addition to the GDPR, EU data protection legislation also includes the Law Enforcement Directive (2016)¹⁷ and the Data Protection Regulation govern-

¹⁷ See: Directive (EU) 2016/680 of the EP and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by competent authorities for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, and on the free movement of such data, which entered into force on 5 May 2016 and EU Member States had to transpose it into their national laws by 6 May 2018.

ing EU institutions, bodies, offices, and agencies (2018).¹⁸ To ensure that EU data protection legislation is applied consistently, national and European data protection authorities and bodies have been established (European Data Protection Supervisor, European Data Protection Board, etc.). Notably, after the first EC Report on the application of the GDPR (2020), the Second EC Report (2024)¹⁹ concluded that, in the six years since the GDPR entered into effect, it has empowered people by granting them greater control over their personal data. In May 2025, in order to continuously improve the protection of individuals' personal data, the Council and European Parliament agreed to lay down new procedural rules on the enforcement of the GDPR. The new law aims to ensure faster and more effective GDPR enforcement in cross-border cases.

4. Digital transformation and personal data protection

Under the OECD Digital Government Policy Framework, digital government is characterized by six core dimensions: Digital by design; Data-driven public sector; Government as a platform; Open by default; User-driven; and Proactiveness (OECD, 2020: 6). In order to fully adapt to and reap the benefits of the digital age, the public sector needs to be “digital by design”. It means that the public sector needs to embrace digital technology, innovate public services and data processing practices to transform the interaction with the users of public services, through sustainable policy and throughout the service lifecycle. Governments need to ensure that the public sector is equipped to effectively design and implement digital government strategies (OECD, 2020: 8).

Starting from the fact that digital technologies have transformed the economy and society, affecting all sectors of activity and the daily lives of all citizens, and that data are at the center of this transformation, the EU has adopted a European strategy for data (2020).²⁰ The data strategy aims to create a single market for data, where data flows freely within the EU and

¹⁸ See: Regulation (EU) 2018/1725 of the EP and of the Council of 23 October 2018 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by the Union institutions, bodies, offices and agencies and on the free movement of such data, which entered into force on 11 December 2018.

¹⁹ See: EC Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council: Second Report on the application of the General Data Protection Regulation, COM/2024/357, Brussels, 25.7.2024; <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM:2024:357:FIN&qid=1721897017650>.

²⁰ EUR-Lex: EC Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee, and the Committee of the Regions: A

across sectors for the benefit of businesses, researchers and public administrations. The pillars of the data strategy are the Data Governance Act (2022)²¹ and the Data Act (2023).²² The Data Governance Act stipulates concrete rules on the re-use of public sector data containing personal data, lays down a legislative framework for data intermediation services, including personal information management services or personal data clouds offered in order to empower data subjects when exercising their rights under the GDPR. The Data Act strengthens data subjects' control over the data they generate by using smart objects they own, rent or lease and mandates technical requirements for data access and portability (EC, 2024a: 17).²³

In order to support the consistent application of the data protection framework in relation to new technologies, while supporting innovation and technological developments, EU has adopted a range of initiatives, some of which complement the GDPR or specify how it should be applied in specific areas, in order to pursue particular objectives. In this regard, the Digital Services Act (DSA, 2022)²⁴ aims to provide a safe online environment for individuals and business by prohibiting online platforms from showing advertisements based on profiling (as defined in the GDPR) by using 'special categories of personal data' (Recital 69, DSA). The DSA regulates online intermediaries and platforms, such as marketplaces, social networks, content-sharing platforms, app stores, and online travel and accommodation platforms. It ensures user safety, protects fundamental rights, and creates a fair and open online platform environment. To make digital markets fairer and more contestable, the Digital Markets Act (DMA, 2022)²⁵ prohibits operators designated as 'gatekeepers' from 'combining' and 'cross-using' personal data between their core platform services and other services unless the user has

European strategy for data, COM (2020) 66 final, Brussels, 19.2.2020; available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52020DC0066>.

²¹ Regulation (EU) 2022/868 (Data Governance Act) OJ L 152, 3.6.2022.

²² Regulation (EU) 2023/2854 (Data Act) OJ L, 2023/2854, 22.12.2023.

²³ European Commission (2024a). Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council: *Second Report on the application of the General Data Protection Regulation*, COM/2024/357 final, Brussels, 25.7.2024; <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52024DC0357>.

²⁴ Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 October 2022 on a Single Market For Digital Services, and amending Directive 2000/31/EC (Digital Services Act), PE/30/2022/REV/1, OJ L 277, 27.10.2022 ; available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2022/2065/oj/eng>.

²⁵ Regulation (EU) 2022/1925 of the European Parliament and of the Council (Digital Markets Act) OJ L 265, 12.10.2022, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2022/1925/oj/eng>.

provided express consent, as defined in the GDPR. Additionally, the AI Act (2024)²⁶ specifies the EU data protection rules in specific areas where AI is used, such as remote biometric identification systems, the processing of special categories of data to detect bias, and the further processing of personal data in regulatory sandboxes (EC, 2024a: 16).

In an endeavour to shape the rights of individuals in the digital society, the EU adopted the European Declaration on Digital Rights and Principles for the Digital Decade (2023/C23/01).²⁷ It specifies that “Everyone has the right to privacy and the right to personal data protection. The latter right includes the control by individuals on how their personal data are used and with whom they are shared” (Article 17). In addition, “everyone has the right to the confidentiality of their communications and the information on their electronic devices, and not to be subjected to unlawful online surveillance, unlawful pervasive tracking or interception measures” (Article 18 of the Declaration).

In recent years, the development and application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) have become increasingly significant. AI systems may process vast amounts of data, learn from patterns and feedback, and perform complex tasks that would otherwise require human expertise or intervention. Thus, AI is identified as an interdisciplinary field of research, which receives special attention in society, economy and the public sector (Milovanović, 2023: 7).

The CoE Framework Convention on Artificial Intelligence and Human Rights, Democracy and the Rule of Law (2024)²⁸ is the first-ever international legally binding treaty in this field. The Convention complements existing international standards on human rights, democracy and the rule of law, and aims to fill any legal gaps that may result from rapid technological advances. It envisages that activities within the AI systems lifecycle must comply with the fundamental principles: human dignity and individual autonomy; equal-

²⁶ Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council (Artificial Intelligence Act), OJ L, 2024/1689, 12.07.2024; <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1689/oj/eng>.

²⁷ The European Declaration on Digital Rights and Principles for the Digital Decade (2023/C 23/01), joint declaration of the European Parliament, the Council, and the Commission, C 23/2, OJ of the EU, 23.1.2023, [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32023C0123\(01\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32023C0123(01)).

²⁸ CoE Framework Convention on Artificial Intelligence and Human Rights, Democracy and the Rule of Law, Vilnius, 5.IX.2024, Council of Europe Treaty Series - No. 225, opened for signature in 2024; <https://rm.coe.int/1680afae3c>.

ity and non-discrimination; respect for privacy and personal data protection; transparency and oversight; accountability and responsibility; reliability and safe innovation (Articles 6-13 of the Framework Convention). The AI Act entered into force on 1 August 2024, as the first act to lay the foundations for the complex regulation of AI in the EU. The regulation aims to ensure security, transparency and compliance with European values in the development and use of AI (Jakubek-Lalik, 2024: 114).

Many AI applications process personal data. On the one hand, personal data may contribute to the data sets used to train machine learning systems, i.e. build their algorithmic models. On the other hand, such models can be applied to personal data to make inferences on particular individuals. The AI-based processing of vast amounts of data on individuals and their interactions has social significance: it provides opportunities for social knowledge and better governance, but it also entails risks leading to the extremes of 'surveillance capitalism' and 'surveillance state' (European Parliament/EP, 2020: 1). A number of AI-related ethical and legal issues have already emerged in several domains: civil liability, insurance, data protection, safety, contracts, and crimes. Many AI applications involve mass processing of personal data, including the targeting and personalised treatment of individuals. It explains why data protection is the area of law that has engaged with AI most, although other areas are involved as well. The GDPR does not explicitly mention AI but it contains some Internet-related terms (social networks, website, links, etc.). Yet, many GDPR provisions are very relevant to AI (EP, 2020:1).

AI systems enable automated decision-making even in domains that require complex choices. In many cases, automated predictions and decisions are not only cheaper but also more precise and impartial than human ones, as AI systems can avoid the typical fallacies of human psychology. However, algorithmic decisions may also be mistaken or discriminatory, reproducing human biases and generating new one (EP, 2020: 35). It should be noted that the existing regulations on personal data protection do not address the systemic challenges linked to automated decision-making. The GDPR and the Convention 108 provisions primarily focus on solutions such as prohibition of automated decision-making (ADM) or providing access to the logic behind a particular decision. Anyway, the ADM and AI-supported decision-making generate new dilemmas, especially pertaining to accountability, data protection, and general administrative law principles (Jakubek-Lalik, 2024: 115).

Despite the efforts and increased investment in AI research, there is still insufficiently broad discussion on its use in the public sector. It is stated that AI can greatly help improve the quality of public administration work, which

has a direct positive impact on citizens, by ensuring compliance with the standards of public service provision, increasing their effectiveness, the ability to adapt to the specific needs of certain categories of service users, etc. (Milovanović, 2023: 13). Indeed, the implementation of AI in public administration has enormous potential but it also brings a number of challenges. It is crucial that the public, government and local administration use AI in a transparent manner, respecting the rights of citizens and ensuring high standards of data protection, as well as providing effective legal remedies in case of any mistakes (Jakubek-Lalik, 2024: 124). The improper use of AI may result in violation or limitation of fundamental rights, including the rights to privacy and personal data protection. In general, an individual can agree or object to data processing. However, in the public sector, where the use of information technologies is usually prescribed by law, an individual has no right to object about data processing or the use of AI technologies for such purposes (Milovanović, 2023: 14).

5. Data privacy challenges in digital transformation

In the contemporary society characterized by technological advancement, it is highly important to ensure the protection of individual rights from other people's misuse. Due to the growing number of identity theft, data breach and cybercrime cases, it is essential to provide better policies to prevent such incidence and to ensure respect for user's data by establishing more rigorous policies (Gunuganti, 2018: 358).

Despite the appropriate technical and organisational measures that should be used by controllers to ensure an adequate security level while processing personal data, breaches can still occur. Article 4 (12) of GDPR defines a personal data breach as “a breach of security leading to the accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorized disclosure of, or access to, personal data transmitted, stored or otherwise processed”. A data breach is an intentional or unintentional release of secure or private/confidential information into an untrusted environment. Other terms for this phenomenon include unintentional information disclosure, data leak, information leakage, and data spill (Srinivas, Liang, 2022: 113, 115).

Digital transformation in society has led to data breaches, identity theft and personal data misuse in the private and public sectors alike. Security of digital infrastructure has become a key challenge for governments. Estonia is one of the models for the provision of public services via digital channels, where 99% of public services are available through such channels. The Estonian government has adopted blockchain-based security to secure its digital

infrastructure. Despite these robust security mechanisms, an increase in cyber-attacks was reported in the 2023 annual report, resulting in billions of Euros in losses. Although such digital initiatives modernize the provision of government services, privacy protection should also be a key consideration (Saeed, 2025: 3). These issues may be illustrated by several cases on personal data breaches.

In one of the major data breaches in the USA, hackers stole the personal information of 2.9 billion people, including full names, addresses, birth dates, phone numbers, and social security numbers. The sensitive data were leaked on the dark web, four months after the National Public Data (NPD) company was breached by a hacking group. The scale of this cyber hack raised concerns about identity theft.²⁹ Another example is the Nashville-based HCA Healthcare,³⁰ comprising 180 hospitals and 2,300 ambulatory care sites in 20 states and in the United Kingdom, which discovered that an unknown and unauthorized party posted their patients' data on an online forum, including patient's name, city, state, zip code; email, phone number, birth date, gender; service date, location and appointment date. In another case, the Dutch government reported to have lost two external hard disks storage devices with personal data of more than 6.9 million registered organ donors. The hard drives stored electronic copies of donor forms filed with the Dutch Donor Register from February 1998 to June 2010, including first and last name, gender, birth date, address, ID number, user's signature, and choice for organ donations.³¹

The issue of privacy and personal data protection is often associated with the use of social networks. In September 2016, at least 500 million records from Yahoo were stolen, including dates of birth, names, and security information, which was the largest data breach in history at the time.³² Facebook, or Meta, has faced numerous privacy concerns. Back in 2018, it was revealed

²⁹ Tech.co (2024). Your Social Security Number Has Probably Been Stolen – Here's What To Do (by I. O'Sullivan), 16 August 2024; available at: <https://tech.co/news/social-security-number-stolen-advice>.

³⁰ HCA Healthcare (2023). HCA Healthcare Reports: Data Security Incident, 10 July 2023, <https://investor.hcahealthcare.com/news/news-details/2023/HCA-Healthcare-Reports-Data-Security-Incident/default.aspx>.

³¹ ZD Net (2020). Dutch government loses hard drives with data of 6.9 million registered donors (by C. Cimpanu), 11.3.2020, <https://www.zdnet.com/article/dutch-government-loses-hard-drives-with-data-of-6-9-million-registered-donors/>.

³² CNBC (2016). Yahoo data breach is among the biggest in history (by M. Fahey, N. Wells), 22.Sept. 2016, <https://www.cnn.com/2016/09/22/yahoo-data-breach-is-among-the-biggest-in-history.html>.

that the data marketing company had illegally harvested the personal data of more than 80 million Facebook users. In March 2021, a whopping 533 million user records from 106 countries were posted onto a hacking forum including full names, phone numbers, user locations, biographical information, and email addresses.³³ There are other examples involving the violation of privacy rights, for example of children on TikTok. In May 2025, the Irish Supervisory Authority fined TikTok €530 million for violating user data protection rules as TikTok's transfers to China infringed Article 46(1) GDPR because it failed to verify, guarantee and demonstrate that the supplementary measures and the Standard Contractual Clauses were effective to ensure that the personal data of EEA users transferred via remote access were afforded a level of protection essentially equivalent to that guaranteed within the EU.³⁴

Serious concerns have been raised in Italy over the collection, use and storage of users' personal data when using ChatGPT. In 2023, the Italian data protection authority imposed a temporary ban on OpenAI for mass collection and storage of personal data for the purpose of training the ChatGPT algorithms.³⁵ In 2024, OpenAI was fined €15mil for breach of privacy rules, lack of transparency in data processing, and unlawful personal data use.³⁶

6. Digital transformation and personal data protection in North Macedonia

In North Macedonia, Article 18 of the Constitution from 1991³⁷ guarantees the security and confidentiality of personal data, as well as protection against any violation of personal integrity in the course of data processing

³³ Business Insider (2021). Stolen data of 533 million Facebook users leaked online, (by A. Holmes), <https://www.businessinsider.com/stolen-data-of-533-million-facebook-users-leaked-online-2021-4?r=US&IR=T>.

³⁴ EDPB/European Data Protection Board (2025). Irish Supervisory Authority fines TikTok €530 million and orders corrective measures following Inquiry into transfers of EEA User Data to China, 4 July 2025, https://www.edpb.europa.eu/news/news/2025/irish-supervisory-authority-fines-tiktok-eu530-million-and-orders-corrective_en.

³⁵ BBC (2023). ChatGPT banned in Italy over privacy concerns (by Sh. McCallum), 1 April 2023, <https://www.bbc.com/news/technology-65139406>.

³⁶ Reuters (2024). Italy fines OpenAI over ChatGPT privacy rules breach (by E. Pollina, A. Armelini), 20. Dec.2024; <https://www.reuters.com/technology/italy-fines-openai-15-million-euros-over-privacy-rules-breach-2024-12-20/>.

³⁷ The Constitution of the Republic of North Macedonia, *Official Gazette of the Republic of Macedonia*, No. 52/91 <https://www.slvesnik.com.mk/content/pdf/USTAV-eng.pdf>.

and personal data registration. Under Article 25 of the Constitution, “every citizen is guaranteed the respect and protection of privacy of personal and family life, dignity and reputation”.

The Macedonian legislative framework includes the first Personal Data Protection Act (1994), the second Personal Data Protection Act (2005) which was amended and supplemented several times, and the latest Personal Data Protection Act (2020)³⁸ (hereinafter: the PDP Act) which has been harmonized with the EU regulations in this field, particularly with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).³⁹ The latest PDP Act (2020) regulates the rights to privacy and personal data protection in connection with personal data processing, the personal data processing principles, rights of the personal data subjects, obligations of controller and processor, the transfer of personal data to another country, special personal data processing operations, responsibilities in personal data processing, legal remedies and supervision over the personal data protection, related misdemeanor offences and misdemeanor proceedings, as well as the establishment, status and competences of the Personal Data Protection Agency.

In line with contemporary trends, North Macedonia has adopted appropriate legal frameworks governing the use of e-government, aimed at facilitating the efficient and effective delivery of electronic services, including but not limited to: the Act on Electronic Management and Electronic Services, the Act on Electronic Documents, e-ID and Confidential Services, the General Administrative Procedure Act (GAPA), the Personal Data Protection Act, the Central Population Register Act, and the Act on Free Access to Public Information. The first three acts regulate electronic public administration, providing a basis for the delivery of electronic services to citizens, electronic identification, use of electronic signatures, electronic delivery of documents between authorities, and establishment and operation of the National Portal for electronic services, the Catalogue of Services, and a Single Point for Services. The GAPA is a general legislative act regulating the practical application of ICT solutions in all administrative proceedings and paving the way to more efficient, simpler and faster administrative procedures that facilitate economic activities. One of the key GAPA provisions regulates the responsibility for the collection of evidence ex officio and electronically by the insti-

³⁸ The Personal Data Protection Act, *Official Gazette of the Republic of North Macedonia*, No. 42/20, 294/21 and 101/25.

³⁹ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the EP and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (General Data Protection Regulation).

tutions; it practically establishes a one-stop shop system which entails the integration and rationalization of public services from the point of view of the parties.

The Ministry for Information Society and Administration (MISA) was established in 2008 by the Act on the Organization and Operation of State Administration Bodies (OOSAB Act), as a body with competences in the public and state administration. The MISA was responsible for the creation and development of an information society (planning, management and approval of all ICT-related projects in the Government and state institutions) as well as for the promotion and wider use of ICT. It also had broad competences in the field of electronic operations and the provision of electronic services, including the supervision of the application of laws in this area. Under the amended OOSAB Act (2024), the MISA was divided into the Ministry of Public Administration and the Ministry of Digital Transformation. While the former remains responsible for the state and public administration, including its reform, the latter is inter alia in charge of the tasks related to the development and promotion of the information society, preparation of strategic documents in the field of digitization, security of networks and information systems, digitalization of public services, etc. (Akimovska Maletić, 2024: 130).

Regarding personal data protection, reports suggests that no progress has been made. Namely, full alignment with the GDPR is still pending, as is the adoption of national legislation to align with the EU Law Enforcement Directive. The Personal Data Protection Agency performance is restricted due to the lack the independence to autonomously hire staff and spend its budget. This, along with insufficient funds, prevents the Agency from carrying out its tasks and powers in full. The Agency is not systematically consulted on sectoral laws or implementing legislation. Coordination, communication and responsiveness to the Agency recommendations is still insubstantial. There is no follow-up in the Macedonian Parliament on the Agency annual report and reports on specific issues, such as the interception of communication (European Commission/EC, 2024b: 35). As for digital transformation, the conclusion is that the country is moderately prepared. There is a lack of appropriate strategic framework to enhance and strengthen digital government, such as the National ICT Strategy. Yet, the PAR Strategy 2023-2030 is the main strategic document in the service delivery area. The priority area of “service delivery and digital transformation” includes concrete policy objectives, outcome-level indicators, baseline and target values. The general objective is digitalised public administration (OECD/SIGMA, 2025: 99). Another important document within the national digital transformation

framework is the Cyber Security Strategy 2025-2028, adopted at the outset of 2025. Given that the security of information systems (cyber security) is a key national priority, this Strategy aims to safeguard the digital infrastructure and services used by citizens, state and public institutions and the economy. Most administrative services in the country are offered both offline and online through the National e-Services Portal (NeSP),⁴⁰ which needs to be further improved. In July 2024, the number of registered users was about 130,000, which is a modest figure for North Macedonia's population. Similarly, the digitalisation level of public services was still low, with just 264 electronic services listed in the NeSP (OECD/SIGMA, 2025: 96). Currently, there are 312 electronic services whereby 202 electronic services are available via the National e-Services Portal. On 10 September 2025, the NeSP system recorded 189,232 registered users and 246,955 users on a single announcement system (Ministry of Digital Transformation RNM, 2025).⁴¹

Overall, it may be concluded that the existing legal framework, institutional set-up and related strategies and guidance in the public service delivery and digitalisation area in the Republic of North Macedonia are moderately in line with the Public Administration Principles. In terms of the criteria related to the implementation practice, the ultimate performance and results in these areas are even weaker. The service delivery to citizens and businesses needs to be further improved. Artificial Intelligence is being piloted in the use of emergency number 112 for real time transcription and translation. State institutions need to further strengthen their infrastructure and ensure expertise on cybersecurity (EC, 2024b: 68).

7. Conclusions

Digital communication, operation and provision of digital services have long been essential in the public and private sectors alike. To support a more advanced and secure digital transformation of society, it is not enough to focus solely on the development of ICT and the adoption of technical solutions. It is equally important to establish and continuously improve appropriate legal frameworks, not only in order to facilitate the implementation of digital systems but also to ensure the protection of citizens' privacy and personal data.

⁴⁰ See: Ministry of Digital Transformation RNM (2025). the National e-Services Portal of the Republic of North Macedonia (*Националниот Портал за е-Услуги*), <https://uslugi.gov.mk/> (accessed on 10.9. 2025).

⁴¹ Statistical data are available at the National e-Services Portal, last accessed on 10 September 2025.

The existing international framework provides a strong basis for personal data protection, particularly in the digital environment, as well as for addressing new challenges related to evolving AI systems. To a large extent, the GDPR has been a significant turning point in the evolution of data protection and privacy as its impact extends beyond the EU, influencing data protection regulations and practices globally. The impact and significance of this regulation is reflected in the fact that it has highlighted the need for global harmonization and interoperability of data protection frameworks. In the increasingly widespread digital environment, it is crucial to ensure consistent and compatible data protection standards across borders. Moreover, considering the complexities of GDPR compliance, it is crucial to foster a culture of data ethics and accountability of alternative data governance models. In the future, there will be an increasing need to consider the societal and economic impacts of data protection regulations and how they will shape the digital environment. Therefore, joint contributions from various disciplines (such as law, technology, sociology and ethics) will be needed in developing comprehensive and adaptable frameworks for data protection in the face of rapid technological change. To strike the right balance between protecting individual privacy rights and fostering innovation, it is essential to explore frameworks and approaches that enable responsible use of personal data while protecting individual rights. This may include the development of privacy-enhancing technologies, the promotion of data minimization and purpose limitation, and the exploration of alternative data governance models (Ullagaddi, 2024: 33).

State and administrative bodies, as well as states in general, must adapt to the modern trends and exert more effort in achieving a higher degree of digital transformation of society. However, we cannot expect significant progress in the digital transformation process, the provision of digital services to citizens and the protection of their data until a comprehensive regulation is adopted in line with international standards, starting from strategic documents in the field, their application through appropriate legislation and their full implementation in practice. As for North Macedonia, the presented objections on the incomplete alignment with the GDPR, unadopted ICT Strategy and insufficient progress in the provision of public digital services aim to urge a proactive approach to resolving these issues and promoting personal data protection.

As technology continues to advance and new challenges emerge, such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), blockchain, and the Internet of Things (IoT), data protection regulations will need to adapt and evolve. The understanding the complex interplay between technology, legal regulation and human behavior

will certainly be of great importance, and these issues will need to be further researched and studied. Particular care must be taken when implementing measures or adopting regulation aimed at addressing subject-specific issues, in order to ensure they do not compromise the overall protection of individuals' personal data. In this context, the proposal for a regulation on combating online child sexual abuse material, commonly referred to as the 'Chat Control' or CSAM Regulation,⁴² envisions the mass scanning of private communications, including encrypted messages. Yet, it raises serious concerns regarding compliance with Article 7 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights. In addition, in order to improve the situation in the area of personal data protection in the digital age and ensure consistent interpretation and application of the GDPR and relevant international standards on personal data protection, it is necessary to establish regular cooperation with other sectoral regulators on issues that may have an impact on data protection, to fully support and allocate sufficient resources to national data protection authorities which would enable them to fulfil their tasks, and to promote education on cybersecurity and digital rights.

References

Akimovska Maletić, I. (2024). E-Government and Digital Public Services as Enablers of Public Administration Reform, International Scientific Conference Contemporary Security Challenges and Strengthening the Resilience of the Countries of Southeast Europe, 23-24 Sept. 2024, Ohrid, Faculty of Security – Skopje, Friedrich Ebert Stiftung, Volume IX, No. 2.

Diligenski, A., Prlja, D., Cerović, D. (2018). Pravo zastite podataka. Beograd: Institut za uporedno pravo

Gunuganti, A. (2018). Privacy and Data Protection in the Digital Age, Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research, <https://jsaer.com/download/vol-5-iss-12-2018/JSAER2018-05-12-358-365.pdf>

Jakubek-Lalik, J. (2024). The Challenges of AI in Administrative Law and the Need for Specific Legal Remedies: Analysis of Polish Regulations and Practice. Central European Public Administration Review. Vol. 22, 2/2024.

Milovanović, D. (2023). Upotreba veštačke inteligencije u javnom interesu – mogućnosti, izazovi i odgovornost, Zbornik radova Međunarodni pravni odnosi i pravda, 36. Susreta Kopaoničke škole prirodnog prava – Slobodan

⁴² See: Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down rules to prevent and combat child sexual abuse, COM/2022/209, Brussels, 11.5.2022; <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52022PC0209>

Perović, Tom II/Volume II, Beograd.

Nastić, M. (2021). The Impact of the Information and Communication Technology on the exercise and protection of Human Rights. *Balkan Social Science Review*. Vol. 17.

Ramakrishnan, P. (2022). Technology Neutrality of the GDPR: An Assessment Through the Lens of Artificial Intelligence (November 15, 2022); <http://ssrn.com/abstract=4960908> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4960908>

Saeed, S. (2025). Digital Transformation in Governmental Public Service Provision and Usable Security Perception in Saudi Arabia, *Information* 2025, 16(3), <https://www.mdpi.com/2078-2489/16/3/247>

Srinivas, S., Liang, H. (2022). Being digital to being vulnerable: Does digital transformation allure a data breach?. *Journal of Electronic Business & Digital Economics*. Vol. 1, No. 1/2, 2022, pp. 111-137, <https://www.emerald.com/jebde/article-pdf/1/1-2/111/1518327/jebde-08-2022-0026.pdf>

Thiên Tứ, H.; Kim Thế Nguyên, D.; Khanh, L.Th.; Nguyễn Dũng, M. (2021). Legal Reform Meeting the Need for Personal Data Protection in Digital Transformation, Law Department, UEH University School of Economics, Laws and Governmental management, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam; <https://future.ueh.edu.vn/en/chi-tiet-knowlege/legal-reform-meeting-the-need-for-personal-data-protection-in-digital-transformation/>

Ullagaddi, P. (2024). GDPR: Reshaping the Landscape of Digital Transformation and Business Strategy (Plaster School of Business, University of the Cumberland, USA), *International Journal of Business Marketing and Management (IJBMM)*. Vol. 9, Issue 2. <https://ijbmm.com/paper/Mar2024/-8340436609.pdf>

Council of Europe/CoE (2016). Draft explanatory report – Convention 108 modernised, Convention for the Protection of individuals with regard to automatic processing of personal data [ETS No. 108], <https://rm.coe.int/convention-for-the-protection-of-individuals-with-regard-to-automatic-16806b6ec2>

European Commission. (2024a). EC Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council: Second Report on the application of the General Data Protection Regulation, COM/2024/357 final, Brussels, 25.7.2024; <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM:2024:357:FIN&qid=1721897017650>

European Commission. (2024b). Commission Staff Working Document

North Macedonia 2024 Report SWD(2024) 693 final, accompanying the Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee, and the Committee of the Regions 2024, Communication on EU enlargement policy, Brussels, 30.10.2024

EU FRA/CoE. (2018). Handbook on European data protection law, European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights (FRA) and Council of Europe (CoE), Luxembourg: Publications Office of the EU, 2018: available at: https://www.echr.coe.int/documents/d/echr/Handbook_data_protection_ENG

European Parliament/EP. (2020). The impact of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) on artificial intelligence, EP Research Service (EPRS), 2020, [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2020/641-530/EPRS_STU\(2020\)641530_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2020/641-530/EPRS_STU(2020)641530_EN.pdf)

OECD. (2020). The OECD Digital Government Policy Framework: Six dimensions of a Digital Government, OECD Public Governance Policy Paper No. 02, 7. Oct. 2020, OECD Publishing, Paris, France; https://www.oecd.org/content/dam/oecd/en/publications/reports/2020/10/the-oecd-digital-government-policy-framework_11dd6aa8/f64fed2a-en.pdf

OECD/SIGMA. (2025). Public administration in the Republic of North Macedonia 2024: Assessment against the Principles of Public Administration, SIGMA Monitoring Reports, OECD/SIGMA, Paris, France; https://www.sigmaweb.org/content/dam/sigma/en/publications/reports/2025/01/public-administration-in-the-republic-of-north-macedonia-2024_03a4d4f2/071bad9d-en.pdf

United Nations/UN. (2018). Personal data protection and privacy principles, the UN High-Level Committee on Management (HLCM), 11 Oct. 2018, https://unsceb.org/sites/default/files/imported_files/UN-Principles-on-Personal-Data-Protection-Privacy-2018_0.pdf

Legal documents

CoE The European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR, 1950), amended by Protocols Nos. 11, 14 and 15 supplemented by Protocols Nos. 1, 4, 6, 7, 12, 13 and 16, COE, Strasbourg, France; https://www.echr.coe.int/documents/d/echr/convention_ENG

CoE Convention for the Protection of Individuals with regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data, CETS No.108, (Convention 108), CoE, Strasbourg, 28.I.1981, <https://rm.coe.int/1680078b37>

CoE Additional Protocol to the Convention for the Protection of Individuals

with regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data regarding supervisory authorities and transborder data flows, CETS-No.181, 8.XI.2001

CoE Protocol amending the Convention for the Protection of Individuals with regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data, CETS No. 223, Strasbourg, 10.X.2018; <https://rm.coe.int/16808ac918>

CoE Framework Convention on Artificial Intelligence and Human Rights, Democracy and the Rule of Law, CETS No. 225 Vilnius, 5.IX.2024; <https://rm.coe.int/1680afae3c>

CoE/CoM Resolution (73) 22 of the Council of Europe and the Committee of Ministers on the protection of the privacy of individuals vis-à-vis electronic data banks in the private sector; 26 Sept. 1973;

CoE/CoM Resolution (74) 29 the CoE and the Committee of Ministers on the protection of privacy of individuals vis-à-vis electronic data banks in the public sector; 20 Sept.1974, Committee of Ministers

EC Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee, and the Committee of the Regions: A European strategy for data, COM (2020) 66, Brussels, 19.2.2020; <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:5-2020DC0066>

EC Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council: Second Report on the application of the General Data Protection Regulation, COM/2024/357, Brussels, 25.7.2024; <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM:2024:357:FIN&qid=1721897017650>

EU Regulation EU/2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation), <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj/eng>

EU: The European Declaration on Digital Rights and Principles for the Digital Decade (2023/C 23/01), the European Parliament, the Council, and the Commission, 23.1.2023, [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32023C0123\(01\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32023C0123(01))

Regulation (EU) 2018/1725 of the EP and of the Council of 23 October 2018 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by the Union institutions, bodies, offices and agencies and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Regulation (EC) No 45/2001 and Decision No 1247/2002/EC.

Regulation (EU) 2022/868 (Data Governance Act) OJ L 152, 3.6.2022

Regulation (EU) 2023/2854 (Data Act) OJ L, 2023/2854, 22.12.2023

Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 October 2022 on a Single Market For Digital Services, and amending Directive 2000/31/EC (Digital Services Act), PE/30/2022/REV/1, OJ L 277, 27.10.2022; <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2022/2065/oj/eng>

Regulation (EU) 2022/1925 of the European Parliament and of the Council (Digital Markets Act) OJ L 265, 12.10.2022, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2022/1925/oj/eng>

Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council (Artificial Intelligence Act), OJ L, 2024/1689, 12.07.2024; <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1689/oj/eng>

Directive 95/46/EC on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (Data Protection Directive), OJ 1995 L 281 (in effect until May 2018)

Directive 2002/58/EC concerning the processing of personal data and the protection of privacy in the electronic communications (Directive on privacy and electronic communications), OJ 2002 L 201

Directive amending the Directive on privacy and electronic communications (Directive 2006/24/EC) and (Directive 2009/136/EC), Council Framework Decision 2008/977/JHA on the protection of personal data processed in the framework of police and judicial cooperation in criminal matters and Directive 2016/680 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by competent authorities for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, and on the free movement of such data

Directive (EU) 2016/680 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by competent authorities for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 2016/680 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by competent authorities for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, and on the free movement of such data

Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council

laying down rules to prevent and combat child sexual abuse, COM(2022) 209 final Brussels, 11.5.2022, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52022PC0209>

UN Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), adopted by the UN General Assembly on 10 Dec. 1948; <https://www.un.org/en/about-us/universal-declaration-of-human-rights>

UN International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR), adopted by the UN GA on 19 Dec. 1966; <https://treaties.un.org/doc/publication/unts/volume%20999/volume-999-i-14668-english.pdf>

UN General Assembly Resolution on Human Rights and Scientific and Technological Developments (1968) UNGA 65: A/RES/2450 (XXIII), 19 Dec. 1968, https://digitallibrary.un.org/record/202686/files/A_RES_2450%28XXIII%29-EN.pdf

UN Resolution 26/13 adopted by the Human Rights Council: The promotion, protection and enjoyment of human rights on the Internet, A/HRC/RES/26/13, 14 July 2014, New York; <https://www.refworld.org/legal/resolution/unhrc/2014/en/105395>

UN General Assembly Resolution on Promotion and protection of human rights in the context of digital technologies A/RES/78/213 (2023), 19.12.2023, <https://docs.un.org/en/A/RES/78/213#:~:text=19.,20.>

UNGA Resolution on the right to privacy in the digital age, A/RES/68/167, 18 December 2013 UNGA Revised draft resolution on the right to privacy in the digital age, A/C.3/69/L.26/Rev.1, 19.Nov.2014

UNGA Revised draft resolution on the right to privacy in the digital age, A/C.3/71/L.39/ Rev.1, 16 Nov.2016;

UN Human Rights Council Resolution: The right to privacy in the digital age, A/HRC/34/L.7/Rev.1, 22 March 2017.

Legislation of North Macedonia

The Constitution of the Republic of North Macedonia, Official Gazette of the Republic of Macedonia, No. 52/91 <https://www.slvesnik.com.mk/content/pdf/USTAV-eng.pdf>

The Personal Data Protection Act, Official Gazette of the Republic of North Macedonia. No. 42/20, 294/21 and 101/25; <https://rm.coe.int/lpdp-republic-of-north-macedonia-2020/1680a9ac8a>

Internet sources

BBC (2023). ChatGPT banned in Italy over privacy concerns (by Sh. McCallum), 1 April 2023, <https://www.bbc.com/news/technology-65139406> (accessed on 8.9. 2025)

Business Insider (2021). Stolen data of 533 million Facebook users leaked online, (by A. Holmes), <https://www.businessinsider.com/stolen-data-of-533-million-facebook-users-leaked-online-2021-4?r=US&IR=T> (accessed on 8.9. 2025)

CNBC (2016). Yahoo data breach is among the biggest in history (by M. Fahey, N. Wells), 22.Sept. 2016, <https://www.cnbc.com/2016/09/22/yahoo-data-breach-is-among-the-biggest-in-history.html> (5.9.2025)

European Data Protection Board (2025). Irish Supervisory Authority fines TikTok €530 million and orders corrective measures following Inquiry into transfers of EEA User Data to China, EDPB, 4 July 2025, https://www.edpb.europa.eu/news/news/2025/irish-supervisory-authority-fines-tiktok-eu-530-million-and-orders-corrective_en (accessed on 5.9.2025)

Forbes (2022). What Data Privacy really needs now is a Digital Transformation, (by G. Ringel), 31.3.2022, <https://www.forbes.com/councils/forbestechcouncil/2022/03/31/what-data-privacy-really-needs-now-is-a-digital-transformation/> (accessed 5.9.2025)

HCA Healthcare (2023). HCA Healthcare Reports: Data Security Incident, 10 July 2023, <https://investor.hcahealthcare.com/news/news-details/2023/HCA-Healthcare-Reports-Data-Security-Incident/default.aspx> (accessed on 8.9.2025)

Reuters (2024). Italy fines OpenAI over ChatGPT privacy rules breach (by E.Pollina, A.Armelini), 20.12.2024; <https://www.reuters.com/technology/italy-fines-openai-15-million-euros-over-privacy-rules-breach-2024-12-20/> (accessed on 8.9.2025)

Tech.co (2024).Your Social Security Number Has Probably Been Stolen – Here’s What To Do (by I. O’Sullivan), 16 August 2024; <https://tech.co/news/social-security-number-stolen-advice> (5.9.2025)

ZD Net (2020). Dutch government loses hard drives with data of 6.9 million registered donors (by C. Cimpanu), 11.3.2020, <https://www.zdnet.com/article/dutch-government-loses-hard-drives-with-data-of-6-9-million-registered-donors> (accessed on 8.9.2025)

Ministry of Digital Transformation RNM (2025). the National e-Services Portal of the Republic of North Macedonia (Националниот Портал за е-Услуги), <https://uslugi.gov.mk/> (accessed on 10.9. 2025)

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ЗАШТИТА ЛИЧНИХ ПОДАТАКА У ДОБА ДИГИТАЛНЕ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЈЕ – СТАТУС, ИЗАЗОВИ И МОГУЋНОСТИ

Резиме

У савременим условима, информационе технологије су део нашег друштвеног постојања, а дигитализација постаје суштински део друштва заснованог на новом начину интеракције између људи, компанија и јавног сектора. Дигитална трансформација као процес се све више интензивира, и у том смислу све више индустрија, као и јавни сектор, се трансформишу, у мањој или већој мери. Дигитална трансформација је детаљна процедура која је много више од само имплементације техничких средстава, она захтева нови начин размишљања и деловања на свим нивоима. Данас је прикупљање, чување, обрада и пренос личних података присутно у свакој сфери живота, али је посебно изражено у дигиталној сфери. У том смислу, огроман развој технологије, вештачке интелигенције и IoT-а (интернет ствари) истичу се као главни изазови у погледу обезбеђивања приватности и заштите личних података у савременим условима.

У раду се анализира европски правни оквир за заштиту личних података, почевши од првог међународног споразума у овој области, односно Конвенције за заштиту појединаца у погледу аутоматске обраде података о личности, („Конвенција 108”), коју је усвојио Савет Европе. Посебно се анализира Општа регулатива о заштити података (GDPR), која успоставља заједничке стандарде у ЕУ. Успостављањем кључних принципа за обраду личних података гарантују се права појединаца. Полазећи од неспорног значаја заштите приватности и личних података, као и усвојене регулативе за њихову примену, поставља се питање дали се обезбеђује довољна заштита овог значајног права појединаца у савременим условима, и дали институције и организације могу да је у потпуности имплементирају. У вези са претходним неопходно је да се институције и организације прилагоде, у технолошком и организационом смислу, да преиспитају прикупљање, чување, обраду и пренос

података, као и да унапреде начин размишљања и негују културу дигиталне етике.

Кључне речи: *заштита личних података, приватност, дигитална трансформација, Конвенција 108, Општа регулатива о заштити података (GDPR).*